

DE-EFFICIENCY OF ITALIAN UNIVERSITIES:
A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC, PRIVATE, AND ONLINE INSTITUTIONS

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De-Efficiency of Italian Universities: A Comparative Analysis of Public, Private, and Online Institutions *

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Abstract

This paper investigates the efficiency of Italian universities, comparing public, private, and online (telematic) institutions over the period 2015-2022. This paper is the first study on the efficiency of online universities in Italy. Using a Generalized True Random Effect (GTRE) stochastic frontier model, we disentangle persistent and transient inefficiencies while accounting for unobserved heterogeneity. Results reveal significant differences across university types, especially when research output is included in the production function. Online universities, despite their rapid growth, exhibit lower efficiency scores due to limited research activity. Our findings suggest that institutional missions and structural configurations shape performance, and that efficiency assessments should reflect the multiple universities' goals of teaching, research and third mission.

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1 Introduction

The expansion of the online universities' enrolment shares is the most relevant and most fiercely debated topic in the Italian Higher Education (HE) system, in recent times. In a descriptive important contribution, [Di Santo et al. \[2025\]](#) provide a rich snapshot of the student body that is enrolled into online universities in Italy, in a diachronic perspective that considers the period between 2010 and 2021. Traditional, on-campus public universities and private ones are concerned with this rapid expansion in enrolment in their online counterparts, which is not only enlarging the potential number of HE students, but is also putting a competitive pressure on them (i.e. competing within the same pool of potential candidate students). In general, the goals set by the European Commission for the HE sector suggest the necessity to find tools and instruments for increasing the number of graduates in our country. Indeed, the objective stated is that “(...) *the share of 25-34-year-olds with tertiary educational attainment should be at least 45% by 2030*”; the 2024 edition of the Commission's Education and Training Monitor [\[EU Commission, 2024\]](#) reports that this proportion is currently just above 30%.

In this context, the assessment of universities' efficiency is of paramount importance. We define efficiency as the ability of maximizing the quality and quantity of outputs produced by the HEI (graduates, publications, etc.) given the available inputs (financial and structural resources, staff and students) - see [Johnes \[2004\]](#) and [Agasisti \[2023\]](#) for a methodological discussion. For reaching the targets set by the European Commission, universities must maximize their efficiency, so make the best use of their resources; in this vein, measuring their efficiency is a task that deserves attention by policymakers, HEIs' managers and the wider public. The academic literature in the field is quite rich; various contributions describe the efficiency of Italian universities in specific years and also in a temporal evolution [\[Agasisti and Salerno, 2007\]](#), [\[Abramo et al., 2008\]](#), [\[Agasisti and Johnes, 2010\]](#), [\[Cantele et al., 2016\]](#), [\[Agasisti and Haelermans, 2016\]](#), [\[Agasisti et al., 2016\]](#), [\[Guccio et al., 2016b,a\]](#), [\[Rella and Dipierro, 2025\]](#), [\[Rella et al., 2025\]](#). The phenomenon of online universities is relatively recent, as the number of students enrolled grew substantially after the period of COVID-19, practically; thus, the existing studies tended to exclude them from empirical analyses. The lack of many data from private universities led also to know little about their efficiency (with the notable exception of [\[Agasisti and Haelermans 2016\]](#)). In the current situation, characterised by a more plural HE landscape and by the post-COVID challenges [\[Agasisti et al., 2025\]](#), the current paper aims at providing an updated and comprehensive picture of the efficiency of Italian universities.

In addition to the extrinsic reasons related with EU-level policy targets, there are accountability necessities that justify the interest of analysing the current level of Italian universities' efficiency. First, the HE sector in Italy is heavily funded by the public sector. This is especially true for the traditional, on-campus public universities, that receive an annual block-grant fund named FFO (Fondo di Finanziamento Ordinario, or Ordinary Financing Fund). Its amount grew substantially over time, from around 3.5 billion euros

in 1994 to more than 9.4 billion euros in 2025 (in nominal terms, while the deflated amount is much lower - see Figure 1). FFO accounts for >65% of the total revenues for the traditional, on-campus public universities and using it efficiently is an imperative for them, given the competing priorities for alternative public funding.

Figure 1: Real values are obtained by deflating the nominal values using the Price Index for families. *Source: authors' elaborations on data from (i) Ministry of University and Research, (ii) [Nobili et al., 2025] and ISTAT (Italian Statistical Institute).*

Also, on-campus private and online universities have their own accountability reasons for reducing costs while maintaining adequate levels of outputs (efficiency), as they heavily depend on the fees paid by their students. According to the theory of cost-sharing in HE [Johnstone, 2004, Johnstone and Marcucci, 2010], the students who pay for their education have higher expectations in terms of quality and quality of universities' performance, and can act as interested stakeholders for an efficient use of the resources. A further stimulus for efficiency derives from the ability of HEIs to attract external funds for research. This is true for those funds provided by the European Commission for selective funding, but also for other similar typologies of grants; see an interesting discussion in [Auranen and Nieminen, 2010]. In practical terms, universities which receive external funding for research have the incentive to demonstrate the outputs produced through it, such as academic publications, spin-offs, patents, etc. The efficiency of universities, when read in the medium-long run perspective, can be influenced by three main factors. The first one is the intrinsic heterogeneity of each institution, that can have specific features that can make it more or less able to realise its operations in an efficient way (for example, its traditions in the internal governance and coordination mechanisms). The second factor is the so-called "managerial efficiency", which is the ability of current HE managers

(Rectors, General Directors, Deans etc.) to stimulate high performance in a given year, with the resources available at that point of time. Efficiency can be changed by means of specific rules, or incentives or managerial practices implemented at a given point of time. This efficiency component varies over time, depending upon the actions taken in a specific year. The third component of efficiency is the “long-term” efficiency, which is due to specific features of the single HE institution that cannot be amended in the short-run. For example, the composition of faculty body and/or the general rules for conducting teaching and research activities are typically not varied over single years, and constitute a time-invariant component of (in)efficiency. When implementing empirical analyses of universities’ efficiency, it is important to adopt strategies and methods that allow to disentangle these components of the efficiency. For this purpose, the method developed by [Colombi et al. \[2014\]](#) can be used, and it has been already tested in the context of Italian HE by [Gralka et al. \[2019\]](#).

In this paper, we analyse the efficiency of the three different types of Italian universities (n=84; traditional on-campus public, private and online) in the period 2015-2022. The dataset we use is a novel one that integrates information collected from Statistical Office of the Ministry of Education, Universities and Research (USTAT-MIUR) and InCites (Web of Science - WoS). We are interested in exploring whether is there an efficiency advantage for online universities when considering only the teaching mission, and how the relative efficiency of universities changes when measuring also indicators related with the research mission. Specifically, we would like to answer the following two research questions:

RQ1 Are online learning universities more efficient in teaching compared to public and private universities?

RQ2 How does the measurement of efficiency change across university types when research output is considered alongside teaching output?

This paper advances the current literature in the field by means of three main innovations. First, it represents an updated analysis of the efficiency of Italian universities (until 2022) when considering explicitly the heterogenous composition of the HE sector, where three different types of HE institutions coexist. Second, it is the first paper that provides a dedicated efficiency analysis of online universities in Italy. Third, we focus the attention of this comparison to the differences emerging in calculating efficiency if considering only the teaching mission versus the case where the research mission is also incorporated.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section [2](#) describes the institutional background of HE in Italy. Section [3](#) proposes a theoretical framework for interpreting the problem of measuring the efficiency of Italian HE institutions. Section [4](#) reports the dataset employed in this paper, along with the illustration of the methodology for the econometric analysis. Section [5](#) contains the results, which are discussed in section [6](#). Finally, Section [7](#) concludes the paper.

2 A Snapshot of Higher Education in Italy

The Italian HE system has traditionally been characterised as being composed of public institutions closely managed, regulated and funded by the state. Although private universities have been part of the HE system for over a century (for example, Bocconi University was founded in 1902, the Catholic University of the Sacred Heart in 1921), their role remained minor in terms of students enrolled.

Over the past three decades, however, the system has undergone significant structural transformations, reshaping the landscape of the HE in Italy. The most relevant dimension of transformations has been the increasing competition both among the public universities and between public and non-state institutions. A series of policy reforms, particularly since the early 2000s, introduced market-oriented mechanisms intended to increase the performance and responsiveness of the system, coherently with the principles of New Public Management (NPM). Public universities were pushed to compete for students and resources. At the same time, external competition has grown considerably. Private universities, once marginal actors, have progressively expanded their presence and visibility, attracting more students and increasing their research outcomes.

This phenomenon is becoming increasingly relevant, particularly in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has heightened demand for online tertiary education. In Italy, this has led to the consolidation and growth of online universities (known in Italy as *telematic universities*). The legal recognition of telematic universities dates back to Law 27/2003, which enabled the creation of institutions offering fully online degree programmes with full legal and academic validity. For a comprehensive overview of the legal framework governing the establishment and operation of online institutions in Italy, see [Di Santo et al., 2025](#).

In the early years following their establishment, online universities accounted for only a small percentage of total student enrolment. However, the context is changing rapidly. Between the academic years 2011/12 and 2021/22, the number of students enrolled increased by more than 180,000, making them a significant component of the Italian HE system [\(ANVUR, 2023\)](#). This expansion has contributed to a substantial reconfiguration of the institutional balance within the system. [Figure 2](#) illustrates the enrolment trends across institutional types. In 2021/22, approximately 1.6 million students (82.2%) were enrolled in state universities, 123,000 (6.3%) in non-state universities, and 224,000 (11.5%) in online universities - up from just 2.5% in 2011/12.

In 2022 (the last year of our analysis), the Italian higher education system consisted of 98 institutions with very different characteristics, summarised in [Table 1](#). These Institutions are formally divided into two main categories according to their legal status: state institutions, which include general public universities (*Università statali*) and the highly selective Elite Schools (*Scuole superiori a ordinamento speciale*); and non-state institutions, which comprise traditional private universities (*Università non statali*) as well as the more recently established telematic universities (*Università telematiche*). Although

Figure 2: Percentage of students enrolled in online (telematic) universities and non-state universities over the total number of students in the Italian HE system. *Source: authors' elaborations on data from Ministry of University and Research*

all institutions formally have the right to award academic degrees and are required to combine research with teaching, they differ substantially in terms of governance, funding, tuition fee policies, disciplinary orientation, and course delivery methods (traditional in-person learning or online education).

Public universities constitute the core of the system. With 61 institutions enrolling over three-quarters of all students, they combine a broad disciplinary scope with a relatively low fee regime (about €1,400 per year on average). Tuition levels are not left to the full discretion of universities but are subject to national regulations that link maximum

Table 1: Italian Higher Education system and institutional characteristics, 2022

	State Institutions		Non-State Institutions	
	Public Univ.	Elite Schools	Private Univ.	Telematic Univ.
Institutions (N)	61	7	20	11
Student share (%)	75.4	<1	6.2	10.3
Access to FFO	Yes	Yes	No	No
Teaching model	In-person	In-person	In-person	Online
Avg. annual fee (€)	1,400	-*	8,000	3,000
PhD programs available	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very rare
Access to research funds	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes**
Specialisation	General/Mixed	Highly Specialised	Selective/Niche	Restricted

Notes: * Data on tuition fees for elite schools are not available. **Telematic universities have formal access but limited participation in competitive funding.

fee limits to the institution’s income¹. In addition, recent policy reforms² have reinforced measures to ensure equity of access: the so-called “no tax area” exempts students from low-income families from paying tuition fees altogether. However, the main source of revenue is the Fondo di Finanziamento Ordinario (FFO), which will be discussed in greater detail in Section 3. Virtually all public universities also run doctoral programmes and participate in national and European competitive funding schemes. Nevertheless, their performance remains highly heterogeneous across institutions, often reflecting regional disparities in student demand, faculty composition [Agasisti and Johnes, 2010, Agasisti et al., 2016, Guccio et al., 2016b].

Under the public umbrella, elite schools represent a very small but distinctive segment of Italian HE. Only seven institutions exist, enrolling a negligible share of students. Their mission is to concentrate talent, provide advanced training at doctoral level, and achieve outstanding performance in research and international visibility.

Non-state universities enroll around 6% of Italian students. Their institutional model differs markedly from that of public universities, particularly in financial structure. As they do not receive FFO allocations, their revenues come primarily from tuition fees, which average around €8,000 per year. As a result, the student population is more socially selected, with a higher incidence of individuals from upper- and middle-income families [Triventi and Trivellato, 2012]. Their disciplinary focus is often narrower than that of public universities, with particular strengths in economics, business, law, and medicine. In terms of research, non-state universities are eligible for public research funding and participate in national and European competitive calls. The sector as a whole contributes to doctoral education, though on a much smaller scale than the public universities.

Telematic universities are the fastest-growing component of the system. Their model relies entirely on online teaching, using recorded lectures, e-learning platforms, and remote examinations. Average tuition fees (around €3,000 per year) are higher than in the public sector but considerably lower than in non-state traditional universities, which has supported their appeal for students of all socioeconomic backgrounds. A defining feature of telematic universities is their student profile. While initially they were chosen predominantly by mature students and working adults, recent years have seen a growing proportion of younger cohorts [Bratti and Turri 2024]. However, despite their expansion, doctoral programmes are very rare, and their participation competitive research funding is still marginal. Moreover, telematic universities are constrained in the range of courses they may offer and are largely excluded from fields requiring professional training or laboratory-intensive components, such as medicine, dentistry, and veterinary science.

¹This rule was introduced with Law 537/1993, Art. 5, and subsequently confirmed in later legislative acts

²The D.Lgs. 68/2012 on the right to education and the 2017 Stability Law (Law 232/2016) introduced the “no tax area” and fee reductions for students from low-income families.

3 Theoretical framework: factors influencing the efficiency of different types of universities in the specific Italian context

The theories in the economics of education field provide the lenses through which we can formulate hypotheses about the relative efficiency of different typologies of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)³.

In an economic perspective, HEIs can be conceived as multiproduct organizations [Cohn and Cooper, 2004], which produce different types of outputs (teaching, research and the so-called third "mission") responding to an array of various societal needs - namely, the necessity of educating young adults for the job market, advancing knowledge in all domains and improving societal and cultural life [Agasisti, 2023]. Although acknowledging the importance of third mission [Compagnucci and Spigarelli, 2020], in this paper we do not have reliable indicators for measuring this phenomenon, so we limit our attention to the two early missions, teaching and research.

Universities realise their activities combining several types of inputs (human, financial, infrastructural and technological); in their operations, they might be more or less efficient, with the degree of efficiency being measurable [Johnes, 2004]. In this section, we refer to efficiency as the ability of maximizing the outputs produced (graduates as a proxy for teaching, publications as a proxy for research) given the available amount of inputs (namely, number of students and academic staff).

A first aspect to be considered is that the relative efficiency of universities can be influenced by the different set of incentives they are exposed to. For example, [Agasisti and Haelermans, 2016] demonstrated that Italian and Dutch (public) universities are subjected to different incentives by means of the public funding system; while the former was based on the number of students, the latter was more oriented towards the number of graduates. Thus, the Italian universities appear as more efficient when the model considers students as an output, while the Dutch ones are estimated more efficient when the model considers graduates as output. A similar reasoning applies in the context of this paper, where we are comparing the efficiency of different types of Italian universities. In the Italian HE system, three different types of universities co-exist: (i) traditional, on-campus public universities, (ii) private ones and (iii) online institutions. The government fully funds only the first type, through the so-called "Ordinary Funding" (FFO) that considers a formula which includes the number of (regular) students and the performance in academic

³In this section, we refer to HEIs more generally, but we also use the word "universities" as a synonymous; we are aware that several types of HEIs can behave quite differently than universities, but in the specific case of Italian context the two formulations can be used interchangeably.

research⁴. Private and online universities fund themselves mainly through students' fees and, to a lesser extent, through externally-funded research (this is especially true for private more than online universities). In 2022, government funding covered around 66% of traditional, on-campus public universities' income, with the proportion of revenues from students' fees being around 13% (source: [Mediobanca 2024](#)). The same data for private and online universities cannot be known, unfortunately - as their financial reports are not publicly available; therefore, it can be assumed that students' fees account for more than 75% for both types of institutions [Mediobanca 2024](#). Given the much higher weight of students' fees in private and online universities, they are more likely to pay attention to students' needs and pressures for teaching activities than their traditional, on campus public counterparts. All else equal, this attention can translate into higher efficiency in the teaching mission, for example through better services dedicated to support students or by higher motivation and commitment paid by the students for passing the exams or the attention paid by teachers in preparing their teaching activities. At the same time, a possible behaviour can be that of lowering the rigor in criteria for passing the exam - a quality issue that is very difficult to measure and verify, and that is fiercely debated in the Italian HE context. On the contrary, the importance assigned to research outputs in the FFO would stimulate the traditional, on-campus public universities to pay attention to this mission, so the academic staff is incentivized to put more effort on research than teaching. The efficiency of this type of universities is likely to be higher when considering research outputs in the modelling of their production function.

A second mechanism that can stimulate the efficiency of universities is competition [Jongbloed, 2004](#), [Musselin, 2018](#), [Hart and Rodgers, 2024](#). In the Italian HE sector, the funding mechanisms (both government grants and students' fees) generate incentives to attract students as a source for maximizing revenues, directly and indirectly. Given the limited pool of students in the relevant age, universities are then forced to compete each other. This phenomenon justifies why the online universities aggressively promote their courses to a different, non-traditional set of students, namely those who are already workers and/or older (see [Di Santo et al., 2025](#)). At an aggregate level, the competitive arena might raise the overall efficiency level of the HE system, as all the institutions try to better serve their "customers" (students) for generating higher enrolments in the future years. At the level of the single institution, those that feel the pressure of competition from other HEIs more than others might be more efficient (see [Agasisti, 2009](#)). In the Italian context, this "competition effect" is stronger for private and online universities, given their reliance on students' fees as primary funding source. When modelling efficiency for teaching missions, these two types of institutions could then result performing better than the traditional, on-campus public ones.

⁴The mechanism of the FFO allocations is very complex, and its analysis is beyond the scope of this paper. The interested reader can refer to [Nobili et al., 2025](#); the booklet contains a detailed and well-developed description of FFO mechanisms and evolution over time.

A third point is the different production functions of the various types of universities, particularly when looking at their use of technological innovations. The economic theory suggests that online teaching can be realised in a more productive way than that on campus (namely, with similar quality and lower costs), resulting into higher levels of efficiency [Christensen and Eyring, 2011, Deming et al., 2015]. This efficiency gain should be the results of (i) better use of technologies for personalised education, that would fit more the individual features of students' needs, behaviours, learning times, etc. and (ii) the reduced costs for maintaining infrastructures (classrooms, offices, residence halls, sport facilities etc), and (iii) the reduced costs for teachers, who can teach larger number of students per unit. While the potential benefits of online learning are clear, so are the risks associated with a mass adoption that does not consider the issue of quality at its centre (see an interesting discussion in [McPherson and Bacow 2015]). Anyway, the current literature lacks conclusive evidence about the actual ability of online learning to reduce costs and to maintain adequate quality levels; notably, these two outcomes likely depend on the specific operational choices about how to implement online learning [Soncin et al., 2022]. In the specific Italian context, the fast growth of enrolments in online universities, in the last years, seems driven more by the attractiveness towards non-traditional students and by the promise of getting degrees in an easier (and cheaper) way, more than by the reputation of high-quality education. The Italian legislation surely favours the online universities in the possibility of setting much higher students:teachers ratios than their public and private counterparts. This way, they are in the condition of exploiting scale economies - i.e. by increasing the number of students with the same number of teachers, so reducing marginal costs. If the ability of conducting students to graduation is similar (or higher) than that of traditional, on-campus public universities and private ones, this characteristic should translate into higher productivity and efficiency.

Overall, the forces described in the previous paragraphs can led to a specialization of online universities in the teaching mission - despite a legal status that make them equivalent to traditional, on-campus public universities and private ones, where the co-existence of teaching and research remains central to their mission. In the light of the conceptual discussion proposed in this section, we formulate three hypotheses that we would light to test in this paper:

- H1: *online and private universities tend to be more efficient than traditional on-campus public universities, when considering the teaching mission, because of their higher incentive to respond to students' needs and pressure (as the student in these types of institutions pay a relatively higher fees)*
- H2: *online universities are more efficient than the other types of universities, when considering the teaching mission, because they use the technology in a more productive way to produce higher quantity of outputs (graduates)*
- H3: *traditional, on-campus public universities and private ones are more efficient than*

online universities when considering overall performance, because of their experience in the academic field and a more explicit set of incentives towards producing research outputs (in particular, through the funding mechanism).

4 Methodology, data and empirical model

4.1 Methodology

To explore our research questions and test the hypotheses formulated in Section 3, we assess the efficiency of Italian universities within a stochastic frontier (SF) framework. Universities are conceived as multi-product organizations that jointly “produce” teaching, research, and third mission activities using a common set of resources.

To represent this multi-input, multi-output technology, we rely on the concept of a distance function. It can be defined as either input-oriented (measuring the maximum proportional reduction in inputs for a given output level or output-oriented (measuring the maximum proportional expansion of outputs for fixed inputs). Following the standard approach in higher-education efficiency studies, we adopt the output orientation, as universities have limited control over resources but can influence output levels through managerial and strategic choices [Johnes, 2014]. In this setting, the value of the distance function equals one when a university operates on the production frontier, whereas values below one indicate inefficiency.

Formally, the output distance function is defined as:

$$D^O(y, x) = \min \left\{ \theta \mid \frac{y}{\theta} \in P(x) \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where y and x denote output and input vectors, and $P(x)$ is the feasible output set. Efficiency is thus measured as $1/D^O(y, x)$, with values closer to one indicating higher efficiency.

Within the SF framework, using the GTRE model [Kumbhakar et al., 2014, Colombi et al., 2014], deviations from the frontier can be decomposed into four components: (i) a time-invariant part reflecting unobserved university-specific heterogeneity (v_{0i}) (for example, historical traditions or institutional missions that are not directly observable in the data), (ii) a persistent inefficiency component that reflects structural and long-run constraints (u_{0i}), (iii) a transient inefficiency component that varies across time and may capture short-run shocks or managerial decisions u_{it} , and (iv) a random noise term (v_{it}).

Accordingly, the output-oriented stochastic frontier can be expressed as:

$$-\log y_{1,it} = f(x_{it}, y_{it}; \beta) + u_{0i} + u_{it} + v_{0i} + v_{it}, \quad (2)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ denotes the parametric representation of the output distance function, for which we adopt a flexible translog specification.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Sample (2015 - 2022)

Variables	State Universities		Non-State Universities		Telematic	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Student enrolled (BA)	15,145	12,157	3,797	5,577	9,554	2,545
Student enrolled (MA)	4,745	4,868	1,476	2,246	2,545	3,366
Graduates (BA)	2,660	2,201	938	1,408	1,626	2,448
Graduates (MA)	1,450	1,499	626	967	822	1,435
Number of publications	2,343	2,253	677	1,223	91	74.60
Academic staff	1,180	927	743	1076	326	340
Fees per student	1,412	617	7,712	4,712	3,456	1,861
Master orientation	0.37	0.08	0.44	0.15	0.32	0.13
STEM orientation	0.16	0.14	0.09	0.17	0.10	0.09

Note: Source: USTAT-MIUR; Web of Science (WoS) - InCites.

The empirical implementation of this framework is detailed in Section 4.3, where we describe the model specifications, the choice of the functional form, and the selection of inputs, outputs, and inefficiency determinants.

4.2 Data

The empirical analysis is based on a panel dataset that combines information from three official sources. We collected information on students, graduates, staff, and institutional characteristics from the Statistical Office of the Ministry of University and Research (USTAT). Data on research output were obtained from the InCites (Web of Science - WoS) database, which provides standardized indicators for evaluating scientific production. From the 98 institutions (see Table 1), we excluded some institutions because of structural or data-related reasons. First, some elite schools and specialised institutions were removed, as they focus exclusively or predominantly on doctoral-level education and do not provide full undergraduate and master's programs, making them not comparable with the rest of the system in terms of teaching outputs. Second, two telematic universities were excluded due to missing data on research output, which prevented the construction of consistent bibliometric indicators and efficiency scores. Our final sample comprises 84 universities observed over the period 2015 - 2022.

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the main variables used in the analysis, disaggregated by university type (state, non-state, and telematic) over the period 2015-2022. The figures highlight structural differences across institutions in terms of size, faculty composition, and academic output. Although state universities continue to serve the majority of students, with an average of 15,145 enrolled in bachelor's programs and 4,745 in master's, online universities also exhibit a relevant presence, averaging 9,554 bachelor-level and 2,545 master-level students.

Moreover, differences emerge when considering academic output. State universities

report an average of 2,343 publications per year, compared to only 91 for online universities. This marked contrast highlights the limited involvement of telematic institutions in research activities. Non-state universities, while lagging behind state institutions in research (677), far exceed online universities. In terms of inputs, public universities are also considerably larger in scale, employing on average around 1,180 academic staff members, compared with 743 in non-state institutions and 326 in online universities. These differences in size reflect not only the scale of operations but also the distinctive organizational models and missions of each institutional type. As expected, private institutions charge higher tuition than public universities. Yet, the gap between non-state (in-person) and online providers is considerable: on average, students in online universities pay €3,456 per year, above the public sector average of €1,412 but less than half of the €7,712 charged by non-state in-person institutions. Public universities maintain tuition at substantially lower levels, consistent with their state-funded mission. A similar pattern of divergence emerges when examining programmatic and disciplinary orientation. State universities exhibit a relatively balanced mix between undergraduate and postgraduate education, with an average master orientation of 0.37. Non-state institutions show a slightly higher concentration of master-level students (0.44), while online universities remain predominantly focused on undergraduate teaching (0.32). Differences are also evident in the disciplinary composition: state universities display the strongest orientation towards STEM fields (0.16), compared with 0.09 among non-state and 0.10 among online universities. These contrasts confirm the distinctive missions and structural profiles of the three institutional types within the Italian higher education system. Our empirical approach accounts for these structural differences by incorporating a time-invariant random heterogeneity component in the SF specification (v_{0i}), thereby ensuring that institutional diversity is not erroneously attributed to inefficiency.

4.3 Empirical model

Building on the methodological framework outlined above, we implement an SF approach to estimate a multi-output production frontier for Italian universities. Our aim is to measure efficiency while accounting for the joint production of teaching and research, structural heterogeneity, and time dynamics. We specify three alternative model formulations, progressively increasing the complexity of the output structure and the inclusion of inefficiency determinants.

The first specification (M1) focuses exclusively on teaching-related activities. It includes as inputs the total academic staff (including professors and researchers), the number of undergraduate students, and the number of graduate students. The outputs are the number of undergraduate and graduate degrees awarded. This baseline model is designed to capture teaching efficiency only, without considering any research output or additional explanatory variables for inefficiency. The second Model (M2) extends the analysis by incorporating a research proxy into the output set. Specifically, we include the total num-

ber of scientific publications as a third output variable, in addition to undergraduate and graduate degrees. The input structure remains unchanged. By comparing M1 and M2, we assess how the inclusion of research activity changes the estimated efficiency of different university types (RQ2). Finally, the third model (M3) further builds upon Model 2 by introducing a set of institutional characteristics as determinants of transient inefficiency. Specifically, we include the logarithm of average tuition fees per student, the share of postgraduate students (master orientation index) and the share of programmes in STEM disciplines (STEM orientation), together with geographical dummies distinguishing universities located in the North-East, North-West, Centre, South, and Islands.

The production technology is represented by a translog output distance function, which offers flexibility in capturing non-linearities and interactions between variables.⁵ We also include a linear time trend to capture technological change over the period.

Formally, the empirical model for the case with three inputs and three outputs is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
-\log y_{1,it} = & \beta_0 + \sum_{h=1}^3 \beta_h \log(x_{h,it}) + \gamma \log\left(\frac{y_{2,it}}{y_{1,it}}\right) \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{h=1}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 \beta_{hk} \log(x_{h,it}) \log(x_{k,it}) + \gamma_2 \left(\log\left(\frac{y_{2,it}}{y_{1,it}}\right) \right)^2 \right] \\
& + \sum_{h=1}^3 \delta_{h2} \log(x_{h,it}) \log\left(\frac{y_{2,it}}{y_{1,it}}\right) + \lambda t + u_{0i} + u_{it} + v_{0i} + v_{it}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

In this specification, u_{0i} and u_{it} represent persistent and transient inefficiency, respectively, while v_{0i} and v_{it} capture unobserved heterogeneity and statistical noise. The parameters of the model are estimated by simulated maximum likelihood, following the [Badunenko and Kumbhakar, 2017](#) approach for the estimation of the GTRE SF model.

5 Results

This section reports the main results, discussed in light of the conceptual framework outlined in Section [3](#). We begin by examining the estimation of the production frontier and the resulting efficiency patterns across institutional types. Next, we decompose inefficiency into its persistent and transient components, and finally, we explore how institutional characteristics shape the dynamics of inefficiency.

5.1 Production technology and overall efficiency results

The estimation results for the three model specifications are shown in Table [3](#). Overall, the estimated coefficients behave as theoretically expected, showing stable signs and mag-

⁵As a robustness check, we also estimate a Cobb–Douglas specification. Results are reported in Table [A2](#) in Supplementary material

nitudes across models. Input elasticities are negative, as expected in an output-distance setup, and the time trend is negative across the model, suggesting technical progress over 2015-2022. However, in model specification M1, the coefficient on academic staff (x_1) is not statistically significant, yet the interaction terms involving x_1 are significant, suggesting that its contribution operates through complementarities with other inputs. As robustness checks, we also estimated an alternative specification excluding academic staff. The results remain robust and are reported in the Supplementary Material (Table [A1](#)).

The overall efficiency results are reported in Table [4](#), which provides a broad overview of university performance across the three institutional types and model specifications. Efficiency scores differ both across models and between institutional categories. In the teaching model (M1), the three groups display comparable average efficiency levels, with Non-State universities performing slightly better. Figure [3](#) (panels a–c) presents the kernel density estimates of efficiency for the three models. Panel (a) shows a substantial dispersion of efficiency scores, suggesting that many universities still have significant room for improvement within each university type. Overall, this pattern offers only limited support for H1. Although non-state universities appear marginally more efficient, state and telematic institutions exhibit similar average scores. In general, no clear or systematic differences emerge across institutional types. However, in M2, where research output (measured by the number of publications) is introduced into the production function, important differences emerge. While state universities maintain a similar average efficiency score (0.79), telematic universities show a substantial drop, with an average efficiency of 0.67 (see Figure [4](#)). This decrease highlights the structural gap in research activities for online institutions, whose academic model remains largely oriented toward teaching and thus performs poorly when research is integrated as a core component of institutional output. Albeit to a lesser extent, Non-State universities also exhibit a decline in efficiency, with their average score falling from 0.83 to 0.77. Supporting *H3*, on average, State universities remain the most efficient group, reflecting their stronger research orientation and closer alignment between teaching and research activities.

M3 adds further insight by incorporating institutional characteristics as determinants of inefficiency. In this specification, State universities display the highest average efficiency (0.85), followed by non-state (0.74) and telematic institutions (0.68). Compared with M2, the estimated efficiency scores are slightly higher overall, suggesting that accounting for institutional heterogeneity improves the estimates. However, the main differences across university types remain unchanged, with public universities still performing best when research output is included. Figures [3](#) panel (b) and (c) also reveal a notable dispersion in efficiency, particularly among non-state and telematic institutions. In both cases, the distributions appear somewhat bimodal, suggesting the presence of two distinct subgroups. Among non-state universities, this may reflect a divide between institutions that maintain active research engagement and others more strongly oriented toward teaching. A similar pattern can be observed among telematic universities.

Table 3: University output distance function - Translog specification

Parameter	M1		M2		M3	
(Intercept)	-0.152***	(0.045)	-0.154***	(0.026)	-0.146***	(0.020)
log(x1)	-0.030	(0.021)	-0.234***	(0.033)	-0.195***	(0.028)
log(x2)	-0.235***	(0.034)	-0.204***	(0.037)	-0.251***	(0.034)
log(x3)	-0.778***	(0.037)	-0.568***	(0.040)	-0.544***	(0.036)
log(y2/y1)	0.603***	(0.034)	0.472***	(0.033)	0.497***	(0.029)
log(y3/y1)			0.189***	(0.017)	0.165***	(0.016)
0.5*log(x1) ²	-0.007	(0.034)	0.103**	(0.043)	0.163***	(0.047)
0.5*log(x2) ²	0.230**	(0.096)	0.203**	(0.089)	0.254***	(0.094)
0.5*log(x3) ²	0.324***	(0.093)	0.323***	(0.072)	0.445***	(0.069)
0.5*log(y2/y1) ²	0.454***	(0.070)	0.436***	(0.066)	0.509***	(0.057)
0.5*log(y3/y1) ²			0.008	(0.011)	-0.024*	(0.013)
log(x1):log(x2)	0.224***	(0.047)	0.188***	(0.047)	0.247***	(0.048)
log(x1)*log(x3)	-0.194***	(0.045)	-0.302***	(0.048)	-0.401***	(0.053)
log(x1)*log(y2/y1)	0.246***	(0.041)	0.296***	(0.041)	0.244***	(0.047)
log(x1)*log(y3/y1)			-0.028	(0.017)	-0.012	(0.017)
log(x2)*log(x3)	-0.350***	(0.089)	-0.242***	(0.069)	-0.300***	(0.071)
log(x2)*log(y2/y1)	0.226***	(0.069)	0.156**	(0.067)	0.372***	(0.066)
log(x2)*log(y3/y1)			-0.013	(0.023)	-0.038	(0.025)
log(x3)*log(y2/y1)	-0.326***	(0.070)	-0.312***	(0.064)	-0.427***	(0.055)
log(x3)*log(y3/y1)			0.079***	(0.020)	0.088***	(0.023)
log(y2/y1)*log(y3/y1)			-0.050**	(0.023)	-0.012	(0.025)
t	-0.011***	(0.002)	-0.016***	(0.002)	-0.018***	(0.002)
Random effects component: $\log \sigma_{v_{0i}}^2$						
(Intercept)	-3.711***	(0.145)	-4.587***	(0.232)	-4.445***	(0.198)
Persistent (long-run) inefficiency component: $\log \sigma_{u_{0i}}^2$						
(Intercept)	-3.297***	(0.511)	-2.610***	(0.182)	-2.740***	(0.154)
Random noise component: $\log \sigma_{v_{it}}^2$						
(Intercept)	-5.771***	(0.196)	-6.150***	(0.226)	-6.177***	(0.110)
Transient (Short-run) inefficiency component: $\log \sigma_{u_{it}}^2$						
(Intercept)	-2.658***	(0.330)	-2.638***	(0.335)	-2.553***	(0.670)
t	-1.305***	(0.247)	-1.420***	(0.245)	-1.585***	(0.217)
t ²	0.142***	(0.028)	0.158***	(0.027)	0.187***	(0.023)
Fees per student					2.654***	(0.372)
Fees per student ²					-1.333***	(0.238)
Master orientation					-2.319	(1.552)
STEM orientation					-1.224	(1.186)
Regional fixed effects		X		X		✓
Obs.		672		672		672
Sim. logL		590.45		676.34		716.47

Note: Significance levels: * $p < .10$, ** $p < .05$, *** $p < .01$.

(a) Kernel density of overall efficiency (M1)

(b) Kernel density of overall efficiency (M2)

(c) Kernel density of overall efficiency (M3)

Figure 3: Kernel densities of overall efficiency by model specification (M1–M3).

Table 4: Efficiency Scores by Type of Institution (M1, M2, and M3)

	State Universities				Non-State Universities				Telematic			
	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max
M1	0.80	0.06	0.56	0.92	0.83	0.06	0.62	0.92	0.79	0.08	0.51	0.9
M2	0.79	0.08	0.51	0.92	0.77	0.12	0.54	0.93	0.67	0.14	0.40	0.87
M3	0.80	0.08	0.50	0.94	0.78	0.12	0.49	0.95	0.66	0.13	0.38	0.89

Note: The efficiency scores are derived from the three models presented in Table 3

Figure 4: Overall efficiency by institution type and year (M1, M2 and M3)

5.2 Persistent and transient inefficiency

The GTRE specification allows us to disentangle overall inefficiency into a persistent (long-run) component, u_{0i} , and a transient (short-run) component, u_{it} , see Eq. (2). Figure 5 reports the average efficiencies (M3) by institutional type for the two components.

Figure 5: Mean efficiency over time by institution type: (a) Persistent component and (b) Transient component. (M3)

First, persistent inefficiency (panel (a)) is non-negligible across all groups, pointing to structural factors that are slow to adjust. State and non-state universities display similar levels of persistent (in)efficiency on average, suggesting that long-run constraints are comparable in magnitude despite different funding models. Telematic universities exhibit slightly lower persistent efficiency, consistent with their limited integration in the research ecosystem and narrower programme scope. Second, differences are sharper in the transient component. Telematic institutions show the lowest transient efficiency over most of the period. In line with the negative and significant time trend in the frontier and the concavity captured by the t and t^2 terms in the transient variance (Table 3), all university types experience a visible decline in transient efficiency after the COVID-19 pandemic. Taken together, these results indicate that (i) a considerable portion of the cross-sectional differences are structural (persistent) in nature, while (ii) management capacity and (transitory) shocks on an annual basis further widen the gap for online universities and, to a lesser extent, for state institutions.

5.3 Determinants of inefficiency

The determinants of transient inefficiency introduced in M3, and reported in Table 3, provide further evidence of the dynamics shaping university performance. The estimated coefficients for the time variables in the variance of the transient inefficiency term indicate a non-linear evolution of short-run inefficiency, as it is also clear from the Figure 5. Specifically, inefficiency appears to have declined in the first part of the period, followed

by a partial reversal in the later years, coinciding with the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. This interpretation is consistent with recent findings reporting an efficiency reduction among Italian public universities after COVID-19 [Agasisti et al. 2025].

Turning to institutional characteristics, the coefficient associated with fees per student is positive and statistically significant, while its squared term is negative and significant, indicating a non-linear association between tuition levels and transient inefficiency. Specifically, inefficiency initially rises with tuition fees but declines beyond a certain level. This evidence of non-linear effects is consistent with previous studies showing similar patterns in the relationship between tuition fees and university efficiency [Bolli et al. 2016], [Wolszczak-Derlacz 2017]

Finally, the coefficients for *master orientation* and *STEM orientation* are negative but not statistically significant, implying that these institutional characteristics do not exert a systematic effect on short-run inefficiency once other factors are controlled for. Overall, the results from M3 suggest that efficiency differences across universities are only partially explained by observable institutional features. Instead, unobserved organisational practices, governance structures, and mission configurations, particularly those linked to staffing models and the balance between teaching and research, likely account for a substantial share of the performance heterogeneity observed across universities.

6 Discussion

The results from the empirical analysis presented in the Section 5 provides only a first contribution to the understanding of how the rise of online universities and the intensification of competition are reshaping the higher education sector and what implications these changes may have for universities' efficiency. It is therefore necessary to take into account several limitations and cautions when interpreting our results. At the same time, it is worth noting that our empirical strategy accounts for institutional heterogeneity, thereby limiting the risk that structural differences across universities drive the efficiency results.

Overall, our evidence shows that the efficiency of universities strongly depends on the set of outputs considered and, consequently, on their institutional missions. When efficiency is assessed on teaching outcomes only, telematic and non-state universities do not appear less efficient than public institutions. However, when research outputs are introduced into the production function, efficiency gaps become pronounced, with telematic universities experiencing a sharp decline.

This finding has a clear policy implication: institutional behaviour is strongly shaped by mission, governance, and the incentive structures embedded in funding mechanisms. Public universities operate under performance-based funding (through the FFO formula), which exerts pressure on both teaching and research outputs. In contrast, non-state and particularly telematic universities, which rely almost exclusively on tuition fees, are

primarily incentivised to maximise enrolments and teaching activity. This configuration creates an asymmetry in objectives and resources that must be acknowledged when assessing efficiency [Johnstone, 2004, Johnstone and Marcucci, 2010, Agasisti and Haelermans, 2016].

However, further research is needed to understand the broader implications of the rapid expansion of telematic universities. A first and crucial dimension concerns the quality of both outputs and inputs. Measuring quality is a well-known and challenging issue in efficiency analysis, and it becomes even more complex when modes of teaching and learning differ substantially [Johnes, 2004, Johnes and Perez-Esparrells, 2025].

In Italy, where increasing tertiary attainment is an explicit policy goal [EU Commission, 2024], online universities may play a useful role in broadening participation, particularly for students who would otherwise be excluded due to geographic, professional, or personal constraints [Bratti and Turri, 2024]. Yet, quantity should not be pursued at the expense of quality, as increasing the number of graduates without ensuring adequate learning outcomes may ultimately undermine the very rationale of expansion.

Moreover, recent evidence shows that the student composition of telematic institutions is evolving rapidly. While these universities initially attracted mostly older and non-traditional students, the share of younger cohorts has been steadily increasing, with distinctive patterns in prior attainment and socio-demographic profiles [Di Santo et al., 2025]. These differences have relevant implications for both efficiency estimates and policy design, reinforcing the need for access to more granular microdata on student characteristics, progression, and outcomes.

Equally important is the lack of transparency on institutional finances and cost structures, particularly for non-state and telematic universities. The absence of comparable data on the composition of expenditure, staff contracts, and investment in research infrastructure inhibits any reliable assessment of cost efficiency. Only greater availability and harmonization of data would allow for more accurate modeling of the university production process and a clearer understanding of the trade-offs between access, quality, and efficiency.

Finally, technology itself represents a fundamental but still underexplored component of the production process in higher education. Differences in digital infrastructure, pedagogical models, and content delivery systems directly affect both the cost structure and the educational effectiveness of online institutions [McPherson and Bacow, 2015, Deming et al., 2015, Bettinger et al., 2017]. In the case of telematic universities, technology is not merely a support but a core production factor that defines their organizational design and learning environment [Christensen and Eyring, 2011]. Future research should therefore focus on how technological investment and digital capabilities interact with human and organizational resources to shape efficiency and quality outcomes. Understanding these interactions is crucial to identifying sustainable models of online provision and to guiding policy choices on digital innovation within the higher education system.

As a related point, extremely high student-to-faculty ratios and limited integration into research ecosystems remain salient concerns: telematic universities meet baseline accreditation requirements but underperform on quality indicators relative to other institutions, and several received conditional accreditation in the period between 2018–2022 [ANVUR, 2023].

7 Conclusion

This paper provides a comparative assessment of the efficiency of Italian higher education institutions across public, private, and telematic universities over the period 2015–2022. Using a Generalized True Random Effect Stochastic Frontier model with a translog output distance function, we disentangled persistent and transient inefficiency components while accounting for institutional heterogeneity.

The results show that efficiency patterns are highly sensitive to the definition of institutional outputs and to universities' missions. When efficiency is assessed on teaching outcomes, state, non-state, and telematic universities display similar performance. However, once research output is included, public universities show higher efficiency, non-state institutions occupy an intermediate position, and telematic universities experience a pronounced decline. These results confirm that mission orientation and resource structures play a crucial role in shaping performance.

From a policy perspective, these findings highlight the need for differentiated evaluation and funding frameworks that recognise institutional diversity. Uniform efficiency metrics risk penalising teaching-oriented or access-expanding institutions while rewarding research-intensive models. Policymakers should therefore aim to balance inclusiveness, quality, and sustainability, ensuring that the growth of online and flexible learning contributes to the overall performance and legitimacy of the higher education system.

Future research should further investigate the relationship between technology, organisational models, and performance, as well as the evolving student composition of online universities. Richer data on costs, quality, and learning outcomes are essential to assess how technology can represent an innovation able to enhance both efficiency higher education landscape.

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A Supplementary material

Table A1: Frontier model estimates - Model specification without staff input

Parameter	M0	
(Intercept)	-0.095**	(0.043)
log(x2)	-0.253***	(0.036)
log(x3)	-0.783***	(0.035)
log(y2/y1)	0.572***	(0.033)
0.5 log(x ₂) ²	0.427***	(0.077)
0.5 log(x ₃) ²	0.237***	(0.074)
0.5 log(y ₂ /y ₁) ²	0.333***	(0.063)
<i>t</i>	-0.008***	(0.002)
log(x ₂)*log(x ₃)	-0.387***	(0.072)
log(x ₂)*log(y ₂ /y ₁)	0.318***	(0.066)
log(x ₃)*log(y ₂ /y ₁)	-0.238***	(0.064)
lnVARv0i (Intercept)	-3.478***	(0.141)
lnVARu0i (Intercept)	-4.167***	(0.609)
lnVARvit (Intercept)	-5.764***	(0.187)
lnVARuit (Intercept)	-2.473***	(0.314)
lnVARuit <i>t</i>	-1.266***	(0.219)
lnVARuit <i>t</i> ²	0.132***	(0.024)

*Note: Significance levels: * $p < .10$, ** $p < .05$, *** $p < .01$.*

Table A2: University output distance function - Cobb–Douglas specification

Parameter	C1		C2		C3	
(Intercept)	-0.221***	(0.037)	-0.270***	(0.025)	-0.249***	(0.027)
log(x1)	-0.010	(0.026)	-0.150***	(0.024)	-0.152***	(0.025)
log(x2)	-0.345***	(0.035)	-0.309***	(0.031)	-0.390***	(0.029)
log(x3)	-0.624***	(0.026)	-0.514***	(0.026)	-0.428***	(0.026)
log(y2/y1)	0.480***	(0.026)	0.390***	(0.024)	0.323***	(0.024)
log(y3/y1)	–	–	0.163***	(0.011)	0.161***	(0.012)
t	-0.007***	(0.002)	-0.014***	(0.002)	-0.014***	(0.002)
lnVARv0i (Intercept)	-3.093***	(0.111)	-4.483***	(0.265)	-5.160***	(0.639)
lnVARu0i (Intercept)	-3.074***	(0.270)	-1.761***	(0.077)	-1.623***	(0.080)
lnVARvit (Intercept)	-5.516***	(0.175)	-6.167***	(0.234)	-5.953***	(0.097)
lnVARuit (Intercept)	-2.223***	(0.326)	-2.015***	(0.285)	-0.249	(0.604)
lnVARuit t	-1.324***	(0.232)	-1.355***	(0.185)	-1.597***	(0.194)
lnVARuit I(t2)	0.137***	(0.025)	0.141***	(0.020)	0.180***	(0.021)
lnVARuit fees student sc	–	–	–	–	2.141***	(0.311)
lnVARuit I(fees student sc2)	–	–	–	–	-1.066***	(0.194)
lnVARuit master orientation	–	–	–	–	-5.574***	(1.265)
lnVARuit STEMI	–	–	–	–	-2.947**	(1.196)
lnVARuit geo3	–	–	–	–	-0.350	(0.531)
lnVARuit geo1	–	–	–	–	1.405***	(0.356)
lnVARuit geo2	–	–	–	–	0.182	(0.671)
lnVARuit geo5	–	–	–	–	1.863***	(0.383)

Note: Significance levels: * $p < .10$, ** $p < .05$, *** $p < .01$.